

Citrate Complex of Chromium

K. K. Tripathy and B. K. Patnaik

Chromium citrate complex has been studied by pH titration method. Cr^{3+} reacts with the citrate ligand at lower pH forming a neutral complex C liberating three protons. At higher pH the complex C dissociates to anionic complexes C_1^- and C_2^- in two steps. The equilibrium constants of the reactions $\text{Cr}^{3+} + \text{H}_3\text{Cit} \rightleftharpoons \text{C} + 3\text{H}^+$, $\text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_1^- + \text{H}^+$ and $\text{C}_1^- \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_2^- + \text{H}^+$ are found to be 2.79×10^{-6} , 6.40×10^{-6} and 9.16×10^{-7} at 25°C respectively.

The hydrolytic constant for the hydrolysis of Cr^{3+} according to the equation $\text{Cr}^{3+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{CrOH}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$ is found to be 4.58×10^{-1} .

Ramaswamy and Nayudamma¹ investigated Chromium citrate complex by spectrophotometric measurements and found that Cr^{3+} reacts with the citrate ligand in 1 : 1 proportion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Chromium Perchlorate: Chromium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving chromic hydroxide in a definite quantity of perchloric acid (60%). Chromic hydroxide was prepared by adding ammonium hydroxide dropwise to a boiling solution of chromium sulphate till it was just alkaline and then washing the precipitate with water till it was free from alkali. Freshly prepared chromic hydroxide was then dissolved in excess but known volume of previously standardised perchloric acid (60%) in cold and the solution was then diluted to a definite volume. Chromium content of the solution was determined by precipitation as hydroxide and igniting it to Cr_2O_3 . The amount of free perchloric acid present was also determined and was neutralised by adding the required quantity of standard sodium hydroxide in case of each experiment after the addition of known quantity of citric acid in an attempt to prevent hydrolysis.

The curve A in fig. I represents the results obtained by titrating 100 ml. of solution containing 0.0015 gm. mole of citric acid and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate with *N*/10 sodium hydroxide at 25°C .

The curve B in Fig. I represents the results obtained by titrating the same volume of the solution containing 0.0015 gm. mole of citric acid, 0.000391 gm. mole of chromic perchlorate and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate, (The free perchloric acid present in chromium perchlorate solution was neutralised with required quantity of standard sodium hydroxide solution after the addition of citric acid to the chromium perchlorate solution. The amount of sodium perchlorate thus formed by the neutralisation of free perchloric

acid present in the chromium perchlorate solution was accounted while adding further amount of sodium perchlorate solution in order to bring the total strength of sodium perchlorate to 0.01 gm. mole. The entire mixture was then diluted to 100 ml. by adding required quantity of distilled water, with $N/10$ sodium hydroxide at 25°C . The colour of the solution changed from greenish blue to deep green during the titration.

The curve A in Fig. II represents the results obtained by titrating 100 ml. of solution containing 0.0055 gm. mole of citric acid and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate at 22°C .

FIG. 1.

The curve B in fig. II represents the results obtained by titrating same volume of another solution containing 0.0055 gm. mole of citric acid, 0.0009391 gm. mole of chromium perchlorate and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate with 0.9322 $N/2$ sodium hydroxide at 22°C . (Exactly similar procedure was followed for the neutralisation of the free perchloric acid present in chromium perchlorate solution as it was done in the first experiment). The change in colour of the solution during the experiment is similar to that during the first experiment.

The curve A in fig. III represents the results obtained by titrating 100 ml. of the solution containing 0.005 gm. mole of sodium citrate and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate with $N/10$ sodium hydroxide at 22°C .

The curve B in the same figure represents the results obtained by titrating the same volume of a solution containing 0.005 gm. mole of sodium citrate, 0.0009391 gm. mole of chromium perchlorate and 0.01 gm. mole of sodium perchlorate with $N/10$ sodium hydroxide at 22°C. (Exactly similar procedure was followed for the neutralisation of the excess of free perchloric acid present in chromium perchlorate solution as it was done in previous experiments).

FIG - II

The chemicals used were of "AnalaR" quality and the pH measurements were done with a marconi pH meter. Sufficient time was allowed for equilibrium to be attained after each addition of sodium hydroxide during the experiments.

DISCUSSIONS

The pH value of the system B in each case is lower than the corresponding pH value in system A indicating the liberation of proton due to complex formation.

In experiment II the ratio of metal to ligand is 1 : 5.5. The horizontal distance between the two curves is taken roughly as the measure of the amount of acid liberated (the concentration of citric acid is large compared to the concentration of the metal in solution).

The horizontal distance between the curves A and B in fig. I and fig. II are nearly the same at each pH range indicating the formation of a 1 : 1 complex only. In case of formation of a complex besides 1:1 type the horizontal distances must have been different in both the experiments. Hence it is quite probable that a complex is formed containing only one citrate ligand per atom of chromium.

FIG - III

In the experiment III the pH increases slowly and then rapidly with addition of increasing amount of sodium hydroxide upto the addition of two gm. equivalents of sodium hydroxide per gm. atom of chromium beyond which the pH rises very slowly.

Determination of Equilibrium Constant. The reaction taking place in experiment I may be represented as $Cr^{3+} + H_3Cit \rightleftharpoons C + nH^+$ (1)

The equilibrium constant of the reaction can be represented as

$$K = \frac{[C] \times [H^+]^n}{[Cr^{3+}] [H_3Cit]} \quad .. \quad .. \quad (1.1)$$

where [C], [H⁺], [Cr³⁺] and [H₃Cit] represent the molar concentration of the complex, hydrogen ion, chromium ion and citric acid respectively.

Let A and B be two points in the same pH axis on curves A and B respectively in Fig. 1. The reaction taking place at A is the neutralisation of citric acid and formation of dihydrogen citrate ion, monohydrogen citrate ion and citrate ion. At B the complex C is formed besides the neutralisation of citric acid. The molar concentration of the ions and molecules at A are represented by [] A and that at B by [] B. The pH being same the concentration of hydrogen ion is represented by $[H^+]$. If k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 are respectively the first, second and third dissociation constant of citric acid ($k_1=8.32 \times 10^{-4}$, $k_2=4.07 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_3=3.24 \times 10^{-6}$; (Schwarzenbach and Ackermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32 1682) it can be shown as determined in the citrate complex of cadmium²

$$\text{that } \frac{\Delta [\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta [\text{Ct}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - a/b \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } a = \frac{k_1}{[H^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 k_2}{[H^+]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[H^+]^3}$$

$$\text{and } b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[H^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[H^+]^3}$$

$$\Delta [\text{NaOH}] = [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A$$

$$\Delta [\text{Ct}] = [\text{Ct}]_B - [\text{Ct}]_A$$

$$[\text{C}] = \text{concentration of the complex.}$$

When formation of the complex is complete we have

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{Cr}(\text{CtO}_4)_3] \text{ and hence}$$

$$\frac{\Delta [\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta [\text{Ct}]}{[\text{Cr}(\text{CtO}_4)_3]} = n - a/b \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The values $\Delta [\text{NaOH}]$, $-\Delta [\text{Ct}]$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{CtO}_4)_3]$ and a/b

are calculated at different pH values of the solution and substituting the values a series of values for "n" is determined at different pH values which is recorded in Table I.

The value of n is greater than 3 above pH 4.5 and is greater than 4 above pH 5.5. Hence below pH 4.5 a neutral complex C is formed by the interaction of citric acid and chromium ion with the liberation of three protons. The formation of neutral complex C is complete at pH 4.5 and the concentration of complex C below pH 4.6 is calculated by equation 2 assuming $n=3$. The value of equilibrium constant K is then calculated according to equation-1 and is recorded in table 1. The K values were found to change with pH and the difference in the K values thus obtained may be due to the hydrolysis of Cr^{3+} to CrOH^{2+} according to the equation $\text{Cr}^{3+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{CrOH}^{2+} + \text{H}^+$.. 4

The hydrolysis constant K_h of the reaction may be represented as

$$K_h = \frac{[\text{CrOH}^{2+}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cr}^{3+}]} \quad \dots \quad 4-1$$

Assuming that the hydrolysis is negligible at lower pH the value of K has been found to be 2.79×10^{-6} at pH 2.35.

TABLE I

pH	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^3$	$\Delta[\text{Cit}]$ $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ $\times 10^3$	a/b $\times 10^1$	n	[C] $\times 10^3$	$[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$ $\times 10^4$	$[\text{Cr}^{3+}]$ $\times 10^4$	K
2.35	5.661	0.840	8.859	1.596	0.8513	2.075	97.72	67.84	2.79×10^{-6}
2.7	7.422	1.120	8.310	3.046	1.239	2.080	79.03	54.30	5.769×10^{-7}
3.0	7.672	1.150	7.975	4.822	1.5132	3.268	50.76	47.07	1.368×10^{-7}
3.2	7.722	1.150	7.794	6.197	1.7017	3.544	37.10	42.50	5.645×10^{-8}
3.5	7.760	1.170	7.528	8.951	1.9961	4.034	20.10	34.94	1.817×10^{-8}
3.8	7.620	1.140	7.295	10.52	2.261	4.527	9.344	27.68	6.968×10^{-9}
4.0	7.500	1.120	7.155	12.04	2.441	4.926	5.076	22.29	4.354×10^{-9}
4.2	7.390	1.110	7.034	13.62	2.628	54.34	2.511	16.00	3.398×10^{-9}
4.7	7.180	1.070	6.719	17.87	3.142				
4.8	7.170	1.070	6.649	18.76	3.256				
4.9	7.070	1.070	6.603	19.61	3.350				
5.0	6.950	1.040	6.545	20.49	3.438				
5.1	6.850	1.030	6.498	21.30	3.522				
5.8	6.860	1.028	6.149	26.53	4.212				
6.5	6.740	1.013	5.933	29.16	4.549				
7.0	7.010	1.045	5.843	29.70	4.700				
7.5	7.500	1.118	5.780	29.88	4.864				
8.0	7.820	1.175	5.744	29.97	4.971				

Calculation of hydrolytic constant:—Substituting the above value for K in equation 1-1 the value for $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]$ was determined and $[\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$ was then calculated as follows.

$$[\text{Cr}^{3+}] = \frac{[\text{O}][\text{H}^+]^3}{\text{K} \times [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_B} \quad \text{where } \text{K} = 2.79 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$[\text{CrOH}^{2+}] = [\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3] - [\text{Cr}^{3+}] - [\text{C}] \quad \dots \quad 5$$

The value of $[\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$ obtained is an approximate one. Since the formation of CrOH^{2+} is associated with the liberation of a proton, we have

$$[\text{NaOH}]_B + [\text{H}^+] = n[\text{C}] + a[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_B + [\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$$

$$[\text{NaOH}]_A + [\text{H}^+] = a[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_A$$

It can be shown as before that

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{Cit}] - [\text{CrOH}^{2+}]}{n - a/b} = [\text{C}] \quad \dots \quad 6$$

$$\text{and } [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_B = \frac{[\text{Cit}]_B - [\text{C}]}{b} \quad \dots \quad 7$$

$$\text{and } [\text{Cr}^{3+}] = \frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]^3}{\text{K} \times [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_B} \quad \text{Where } \text{K} = 2.79 \times 10^{-6}$$

The value of $[\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$ obtained above was substituted in equation (6) and subsequently with the help of equation (7) fresh values of $[\text{C}]$, $[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_2$ and $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]$ were determined. Substituting these values in equation (5) a new value for $[\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$ was found out. This process was repeated till the value obtained for $[\text{CrOH}^{2+}]$ did not change. The hydrolysis constant K_h was then calculated according to equation (4-1.) The mean value of K_h thus determined was found to be 4.58×10^{-4} .

TABLE II

pH	$[\text{Cr}^{3+}] \times 10^6$	$[\text{CrOH}^{2+}] \times 10^3$	$K_h \times 10^4$
3.2	8.845	7.2957	5.205
3.5	4.407	6.4516	4.630
3.8	1.778	5.6562	5.040
4.0	1.078	4.9799	4.616
4.2	0.7498	4.0562	3.414

The value obtained for K_h is thus in close agreement with the value given in the International Critical Table. It is mentioned in the International Critical Table (Volume VII, page 286) that Cr^{3+} hydrolyses according to the equation (4) written earlier and the hydrolysis constant for hydrolysis of CrCl_3 at concentration of 6.25×10^{-3} moles/litre at 291°K, 3.333×10^{-4} moles/litre at 291.1°K and 1×10^{-2} moles/litre at 291.1°K are 0.44, 0.51, 0.45 and 0.79 respectively at 0.1 ionic strength..

Above pH 4.5 the value of n is greater than 3 which indicates that the complex C dissociates like an acid to give another complex C_1^- and a proton according to the equation

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} \quad \dots \quad 8-1$$

It can be shown as before that $[\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] = [\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$. Due to the formation of C and C_1^- respectively three or four protons are liberated. The total acid liberated due to the formation of the complex = $3[\text{C}] + 4[\text{C}_1^-]$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{3[\text{C}] + 4[\text{C}_1^-]}{[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]} = n$$

$$\text{or } \frac{[\text{C}_1^-]}{[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]} = n-3 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{[\text{C}]}{[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]} = 4-n$$

The values of K_1 can be determined by substituting $[\text{C}_1^-]/[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ and $[\text{C}]/[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ in place of $[\text{C}_1^-]$ and $[\text{C}]$ respectively. The values of K_1 are recorded in Table III and mean value of K_1 thus determined is 6.40×10^{-6} .

TABLE III

pH	(n-3)	(4-n)	$K_1 \times 10^6$
4.7	0.142	0.858	3.305
4.8	0.256	0.744	5.453
4.9	0.350	0.650	6.779
5.0	0.438	0.562	7.794
5.1	0.522	0.478	8.676

Above pH 5.5, the value of n is greater than 4 and complex C_1^- dissociates like an acid to yield another complex C_2^{-n} and a proton according to the equation.

$$\text{and } K_2 = \frac{[C_2^{-n}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} \quad \dots \quad 9-1$$

It can be shown as before that

$$K_2 = \frac{(n-4) \times [H^+]}{(5-n)} \quad \dots \quad 9-2$$

The value of K_2 thus determined is given in table IV and the mean value of K_2 was found to be 3.16×10^{-7} .

In experiment III the pH value of the system B is lower than that of system A. The curve A is similar to the neutralisation of an acid. The pH attained by the solution containing $Cr(ClO_4)_3$ by the addition of 22.4 ml. of $N/10$ NaOH is reached by the system A by the addition of 1 ml. of $N/10$ NaOH. Hence 21.4 ml. of $N/10$ NaOH i.e., .00214 g. mole of sodium hydroxide is consumed by the complex formed from 0.0009391 gm. mole of chromium perchlorate. The liberation of two protons indicate the existence of the C_2^{-n} complex since neutral complex C is expected to be formed by the interaction of chromium ion and the citrate ligand.

Since the ratio of metal to ligand is 1:5 the formation of the complex is complete. It is found in the table I that the values of n are greater than 4 at and above the pH 5.8 indicating the formation of C_2^{-n} complex. We have here, as the pH of the system above 5.8.

$$\text{Free Citrate} = [Cit] - [Cr(ClO_4)_3]$$

$$\text{But free citrate} = [H_2Cit] + [H_3Cit] + [HCit^{-2}] + [Cit^{-3}]$$

$$= [HCit^{-2}] \times \left\{ \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_3} + 1 + \frac{k_4}{[H^+]} \right\}$$

$$= x [HCit^{-2}]$$

$$\text{Where } x = 1 + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_3} + \frac{k_4}{[H^+]}$$

$$\text{Thus } [Cit] - [Cr(ClO_4)_3] = x [HCit^{-2}]$$

One and two protons are liberated in this experiment due to the formation of the complexes C_1^- and C_2^{-2} respectively.

$$\text{Acid liberated} = [C_1^-] + 2[C_2^{-2}]$$

$$\text{Acid neutralised} = [\text{NaOH}] + [\text{HCit}^{-2}] + 2[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + 3[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$$

At high pH the concentration of H_3Cit is neglected. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} [C_1^-] + 2[C_2^{-2}] &= [\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + [\text{HCit}^{-2}] + 2[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] \\ &= [\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + [\text{HCit}^{-2}] \left\{ 1 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or } [\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3] + [C_2^{-2}] = [\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + y[\text{HCit}^{-2}]$$

$$\text{Where } y = 1 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{k_2}$$

$$\text{or } [C_2^{-2}] = [\text{NaOH}] + [\text{H}^+] + y[\text{HCit}^{-2}] - [\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{HCit}^{-2}]$ from the equation (10), the value of $[C_2^{-2}]$ can be determined. $[C_1^-]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C_2^{-2}]$ from $[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$. The values of k_2 thus determined by equation (9-1) is given in Table V. The mean value of k_1 is 2.55×10^{-7} . This is in agreement with the results obtained in experiment I.

TABLE IV

pH	(n-4)	(5-n)	$K \times 10^7$
5.8	0.212	0.788	4.264
6.5	0.549	0.451	3.850
7.0	0.700	0.300	2.333
7.5	0.864	0.136	2.009
8.0	0.971	0.029	3.348

TABLE V

pH	$[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cr}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cr}(\text{ClO}_4)_3] \times 10^3$	X	$[\text{HCit}^{-2}] \times 10^4$	γ	$[C_2^{-2}] \times 10^3$	$[C_1^-] \times 10^3$	$K_2 \times 10^7$
6.7	11.90	44.06	8.273	17.2449	20.76	1.0098	5.723	2.55	4.478
7.0	13.16	43.42	8.155	33.4024	10.55	1.0049	6.065	2.09	2.902
7.3	14.04	42.98	8.072	65.6512	5.318	1.0024	6.501	571	2.074
7.5	14.53	42.74	8.026	103.4008	3.357	1.0015	6.840	1.186	1.824
7.7	14.82	42.59	7.998	163.4005	2.116	1.00098	7.034	0.964	1.455

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